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COMBINATION OF FULL- AND SPLIT-THICKNESS CORONALLY DISPLACED FLAP WITH CONNECTIVE TISSUE GRAFT IN THE GINGIVAL RECESSION TREATMENT

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Abstract:

Introduction:

Gingival recession often occurs in adults, tends to increase with age, and affects individuals with both low and high oral hygiene standard. The presence of recession is aesthetically unacceptable to most patients, dentine hypersensitivity may also occur, and exposed root surfaces are prone to the oral environment influence and may be associated with carious and non-carious cervical lesions.

Aim: The aim of this paper was to present coronally displaced flap (combination of full and split thickness) with connective tissue graft as a root coverage procedure with minimal/no scar formation.

Case report:

A 22-year-old female patient with excellent oral hygiene presented to the Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina due to gingival recession on tooth 24 (Müller class I) and sensitivity to cold. Apical to the recession, insufficient height and thickness of keratinized tissue was present, so coronally displaced flap in conjunction with connective tissue graft was performed.

Conclusion:

The clinical healing process was complete within 12 months. The root exposure was completely covered with newly formed keratinized tissue. The increase in attached gingival height and thickness with no scar formation was clinically evident, suggesting that the procedure has yielded the desired results.

Key words: *gingival recession/surgery; coronally displaced flap; aesthetics*